

Event title	Portable, reproducible and scalable bioinformatics workflows using Nextflow and Pawsey Nimbus Cloud
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	20/09/2022
Time of event	1pm AEST
Topic description	<p>Bioinformatics workflows can support portable, reproducible and scalable analysis of omics datasets but using workflows can be challenging for both beginners and experienced bioinformaticians. Beginners face a steep learning curve to be able to build and deploy their own bioinformatics workflows while those with more experience face challenges productionising and scaling code for custom workflows and big data.</p> <p>Bioinformaticians across the world are using Nextflow to build and manage workflows. Many of these workflows are shared for others to use and supported by the community via nf-co.re. So far, 39 workflows for omics data are available with another 23 under development. These workflows cover common analyses such as RNAseq, mapping, variant calling, single cell transcriptomics and more and can be easily deployed by anyone, regardless of skill level.</p> <p>In this webinar, Nandan Deshpande from the Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney, will discuss how you can deploy freely available Nextflow (nf.co-re) bioinformatics workflows with a single command. We describe how you can quickly get started deploying these workflows using Pawsey Nimbus Cloud. For advanced users, we introduce you to Nextflow concepts to get you started with building your own workflows that will save you time and support reproducible, portable and scalable analysis.</p>

	<p>In the latter half of the webinar, Sarah Beecroft from the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre will talk about their Nimbus Cloud systems. While Nextflow supports portability and can run on many computing infrastructures, we describe why we specifically love using Nimbus with Nextflow for many bioinformatics projects. We will describe some of the nf.co-re workflows that we have used on Nimbus and the research outcomes. We will also cover when not to use Nimbus and the alternatives we recommend.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/nextflow-nimbus
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Workflows http://edamontology.org/topic_0769 Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Nextflow nf-co.re Containerisation
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for biologists who are new to bioinformatics on the command-line and bioinformaticians and would like to use existing best practice workflows available through nf.co-re.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Outline challenges of working with bioinformatics workflows● Outline how workflow managers can assist with scalability and

	<p>reproducibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe features of the Nextflow workflow manager • Identify Nextflow jargon • Outline features that support bioinformatics on the Nimbus Cloud
Speaker	<p>Dr Nandan Deshpande, Senior Research Bioinformatician, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney</p> <p>Dr Sarah Beecroft, Bioinformatics Applications Specialist, Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre</p>
Related material	None